

A NEW SYNTHESIS OF HEXAHYDROISOPHTHALIC ACID.

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A new method for the synthesis of stereoisomeric hexahydroisophthalic acid has been described.

The condensation of ethyl oxalate with systems like

described by Lapworth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, 79, 1265), has undergone considerable modification recently largely due to the work of Kuhn and co-workers (*Ber.*, 1936, 69 1757, 1979; cf. Pedlar Memorial Lecture, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 610). Borsche (*Annalen*, 1934, 512, 97) has condensed unsaturated nitriles like acrylonitrile and crotononitrile with oxalic ester in the presence of two molecules of potassium ethoxide, but so far no cyclic system has been studied in detail. *o*-Methylcyclohexanone has been converted into the related unsaturated nitrile by the method of Linstead (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 482). This was presumably a mixture of Δ^1 - and Δ^6 -forms. This was condensed with ethyl oxalate in presence of sodium ethoxide, when as has been shown by Lapworth (*loc. cit.*), the Δ^1 -form alone reacts. With potassium ethoxide, the Δ^6 -form also reacts (Borsche, *Ber.*, 1932, 65, 865).

Δ^6 -form

(I)

Δ^1 -form

(II)

To maintain the homogeneity of the product, sodium ethoxide has been used. The oxalo derivative (II, $\text{R}=\text{CO}\cdot\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) has been isolated from the alkaline solution in the form of colourless needles. Attempts to drive off carbon monoxide by heating up to 230° failed, the substance distilling smoothly in vacuum proving its unusual stability.

Similarly Δ^1 -cyclohexene has been condensed with oxalic ester under identical conditions to give (III, $\text{R}=\text{Et}$).

(III)

(IV)

On hydrolysis with methyl alcoholic potassium hydroxide the corresponding acid (III, R=H) is obtained in quantitative yield. Attempted oxidation of the pyruvic acid derivative with hydrogen peroxide in alkaline solution by the usual method is unsatisfactory and consequently it has been oxidised in aqueous solution with hydrogen peroxide at 60°.

The unsaturated *cyclohexenecyano-acid* has been reduced with sodium amalgam and the reduced cyano-acid is isolated as the diethyl ester (IV).

After hydrolysis (IV) gives hexahydroisophthalic acids. From the mixture the *cis*-anhydride has been isolated by distillation in vacuum and converted into the *cis*-hexahydroisophthalic acid (*cf.* Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1891, 59, 808; Cook, *ibid.*, 1936, 68).

The choice of cyanocyclohexene instead of ethyl tetrahydrobenzoate (Kon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1631) for this series of reactions is due to the fact that the reduction of the double bond in tetrahydroisophthalic acid is not possible with the usual reducing agents (Baeyer, *Ber.*, 1886, 19, 1806; Perkin, *loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl (4-Methyl-3-cyano- Δ^2 -cyclohexenoyl)-formate (II, R=CO'CO₂Et).—A solution of sodium (2.3 g.) in alcohol (35 c.c.) was cooled in a freezing mixture and to this was added a cold mixture of methylcyanocyclohexene (12.1 g.) and ethyl oxalate (14.6 g.). The mixture was thoroughly shaken and after allowing it to come to room temperature gradually (15 hours) it was decomposed with ice. The neutral portion was extracted with ether, and from the alkaline portion an oil separated after acidification, which at once crystallised out in long needles, m.p. 110°, yield 8.5 g. It had a characteristic smell and gave a deep violet ferric reaction in alcoholic solution. It crystallised from alcohol in needles with some of the solvent of crystallisation removable on prolonged drying in vacuum. It was unusually stable to heat and distilled in vacuum

at $170^{\circ}/9$ mm. The distillate crystallised at once. (Found : N, 6'51, 6'52. $C_{12}H_{15}O_3N$ requires N, 6'34 per cent).

Ethyl (3-Cyano- Δ^1 -cyclohexenoyl)-formate (III, R=Et).—To a well cooled solution of sodium ethoxide (sodium 6'6 g, and alcohol, distilled over calcium, 86 c.c.), a similarly cooled mixture of cyanocyclohexene (30 g.) and ethyl oxalate (42 c.c.) was added with thorough shaking. On working up in the usual way, a white crystalline substance was obtained. It was distilled at $156^{\circ}/5$ mm., the distillate crystallising in needles, m.p. 196° , yield 31 g. (Found : N, 6'9. $C_{11}H_{13}O_3N$ requires N, 6'7 per cent).

3-Cyano- Δ^1 -cyclohexenoylformic Acid (III, R=H).—The above ester (31 g.), dissolved in methyl alcohol (120 c.c.), was shaken with a solution of sodium hydroxide (18 g.) in water (170 c.c.). After standing at the ordinary temperature for 2 days, the solution was heated on the water-bath for 1 hour and then acidified with ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid when a white crystalline precipitate separated, m.p. $197-99^{\circ}$ (decomp.) after recrystallisation from dilute alcohol, yield 20 g. (Found : C, 60'6, H, 4'6. $C_9H_9O_3N$ requires C, 60'3 ; H, 5'0 per cent).

Ethyl Hexahydroisophthalate (IV).—The above acid (18 g.) was suspended in water (300 c.c.) and to this was added hydrogen peroxide (14 c.c., 28% by titration). The mixture was mechanically stirred and the temperature was gradually raised to 60° . The reaction started with frothing and after about 2 hours most of the acid went into solution and the temperature was maintained at 60° . The solution after filtration was thoroughly extracted with ether after saturation with ammonium sulphate. The ether extract was dried over sodium sulphate, whence a viscous mass was obtained. The yield of the acid from two experiments was 17 g.. This was reduced in a slightly acid solution with sodium amalgam (3%, 800 g.). The operation required about 8 hours and after isolation in the usual way, the yield of the reduced acid was 9 g. It was next esterified with a mixture of alcohol (50 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (12 c.c., *d* 1'84) and heated on the water-bath for 2 days. After isolation in the usual way the mobile oil had b.p. $124^{\circ}/5$ mm. (5 g.) together with a high-boiling residue. (Found : C, 63'1, 63'2 ; H, 8'8, 8'9. $C_{12}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 63'1 ; H, 8'6 per cent).

Hexahydroisophthalic Acid.—Ethyl cyclohexane-1 : 3-dicarboxylate (4 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing with fuming hydrochloric acid (30 c.c.) for 8 hours. The solution was concentrated to some extent when the acid separated as a sandy powder on cooling. It was dissolved in boiling water, charcoaled and concentrated on the water-bath and left aside for crystalli-

sation after the addition of a few drops of hydrochloric acid, m.p. 114-38°, evidently consisting of a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-forms (lit. m.p. 110-30°). (Found : C, 55.7 ; H, 6.5. $C_8H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 55.8 ; H, 6.9 per cent).

cis-Hexahydroisophthalic acid was separated from the mixture by boiling the above acid (2 g.) with acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) for 5 hours and the residue left was sublimed in high vacuum when the anhydride of the *cis*-acid was obtained, m.p. 184° (lit. 185-86°), whence the *cis*-acid, m.p. 161°, was isolated (*loc. cit.*).

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